

GUEST EDITORIAL

ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE: AN EMERGING ART IN PROSTHODONTICS.

The use of technology has had an undoubted support in the evolution of mankind. Innovative advancements in various fields cannot go unnoticed and their role in revolutionizing the operational fields is imperative. Hence, artificial intelligence is gaining support and recognition all over the globe as it fulfills the deepest assimilation of every human being "to work smarter, not harder". John McCarthy- father of artificial intelligence- first coined the term in 1955 and defined it as "the science and engineering of making intelligent machines, especially intelligent computer programs".

Dentistry and specifically the branch of prosthodontics requires a lot of assistance and high-impact, precise decision making due to its complexity and, therefore, artificial intelligence/ machine learning can prove to be a great asset to dental health care professionals. AI has various potential roles in various sub-branches of prosthodontics, namely, removable and fixed prosthodontics, implant dentistry as well as maxillofacial prosthodontics. Digital prosthodontics workflow in the form of computer aided designing/ computer aided manufacturing (CAD/CAM) has become a close-knit part of everyday clinical and laboratory practice. AI also has a pivotal role in diagnostics and AI-based virtual 3D treatment planning can simplify the treatment rendering making it more precise and patient compliant. AI technology could also be used for automatic registering of jaw relationships based on radiological landmarks to simulate individual patient movements for treatment simulation and final fabrication of prosthetic reconstructions.

The future of AI-based learning and practice is definitely bright and needs more expansion that could lead to the emergence of a wide variety of novel options not only in the field of prosthodontics, but dentistry in general.

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